

Elementary particle mixings in 4D

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In a previous article [1], a multitude of 3D particle mixing matrices were derived using Birkhoff's theorem on doubly stochastic matrices; these results are extended here to 4D for future reference.

In 4D there are $4! = 24$ permutation matrices, denoted by $\pi_1, \pi_2, \dots, \pi_{24}$; π_1 is the 4x4 identity matrix. The complete list of these permutations follows.

$$\begin{array}{cccc}
 \pi_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_4 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \\
 \pi_5 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_6 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_7 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_8 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \\
 \pi_9 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{10} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{11} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{12} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \\
 \pi_{13} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{14} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{15} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{16} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 \pi_{17} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{18} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{19} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{20} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 \pi_{21} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{22} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{23} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & \pi_{24} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}
 \end{array}$$

A sorted table useful when computing outcomes of permutation products is shown below; each integer represents the column location of the '1' for each matrix, as rows increase.

$$\begin{array}{cccc}
 \pi_1 = 1234 & \pi_{18} = 2134 & \pi_{23} = 3124 & \pi_4 = 4123 \\
 \pi_{22} = 1243 & \pi_7 = 2143 & \pi_{14} = 3142 & \pi_9 = 4132 \\
 \pi_{12} = 1324 & \pi_{15} = 2314 & \pi_8 = 3214 & \pi_{19} = 4213 \\
 \pi_{17} = 1342 & \pi_2 = 2341 & \pi_{11} = 3241 & \pi_{16} = 4231 \\
 \pi_{13} = 1423 & \pi_{10} = 2413 & \pi_3 = 3412 & \pi_{24} = 4312 \\
 \pi_6 = 1432 & \pi_{21} = 2431 & \pi_{20} = 3421 & \pi_5 = 4321
 \end{array}$$

Consistent with the 3D solution, with $C_j = \cos(\theta_j)$ and $S_j = \sin(\theta_j)$ set

$P_{1,k}(\theta_j) = C_j^2\pi_1 + S_j^2\pi_k$ for $k = 2, \dots, 24$ and $j = 1, 2, 3, 4$. The 23 building blocks are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{1,2}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & s_j^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_j^2 & s_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c_j^2 & s_j^2 \\ s_j^2 & 0 & 0 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,3}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & 0 & s_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & c_j^2 & 0 & s_j^2 \\ s_j^2 & 0 & c_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & s_j^2 & 0 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,4}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & 0 & 0 & s_j^2 \\ s_j^2 & c_j^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & s_j^2 & c_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & s_j^2 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} \\
 P_{1,5}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & 0 & 0 & s_j^2 \\ 0 & c_j^2 & s_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & s_j^2 & c_j^2 & 0 \\ s_j^2 & 0 & 0 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,6}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_j^2 & 0 & s_j^2 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & s_j^2 & 0 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,7}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & s_j^2 & 0 & 0 \\ s_j^2 & c_j^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c_j^2 & s_j^2 \\ 0 & 0 & s_j^2 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} \\
 P_{1,8}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & 0 & s_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ s_j^2 & 0 & c_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,9}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & 0 & 0 & s_j^2 \\ s_j^2 & c_j^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & s_j^2 & 0 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,10}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & s_j^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_j^2 & 0 & s_j^2 \\ s_j^2 & 0 & c_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & s_j^2 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} \\
 P_{1,11}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & 0 & s_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c_j^2 & s_j^2 \\ s_j^2 & 0 & 0 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,12}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_j^2 & s_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & s_j^2 & c_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,13}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_j^2 & 0 & s_j^2 \\ 0 & s_j^2 & c_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & s_j^2 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} \\
 P_{1,14}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & 0 & s_j^2 & 0 \\ s_j^2 & c_j^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c_j^2 & s_j^2 \\ 0 & s_j^2 & 0 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,15}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & s_j^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_j^2 & s_j^2 & 0 \\ s_j^2 & 0 & c_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,16}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & 0 & 0 & s_j^2 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ s_j^2 & 0 & 0 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} \\
 P_{1,17}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_j^2 & s_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c_j^2 & s_j^2 \\ 0 & s_j^2 & 0 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,18}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & s_j^2 & 0 & 0 \\ s_j^2 & c_j^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,19}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & 0 & 0 & s_j^2 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ s_j^2 & 0 & c_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & s_j^2 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} \\
 P_{1,20}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & 0 & s_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & c_j^2 & 0 & s_j^2 \\ 0 & s_j^2 & c_j^2 & 0 \\ s_j^2 & 0 & 0 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,21}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & s_j^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_j^2 & 0 & s_j^2 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ s_j^2 & 0 & 0 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,22}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c_j^2 & s_j^2 \\ 0 & 0 & s_j^2 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix} \\
 P_{1,23}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & 0 & s_j^2 & 0 \\ s_j^2 & c_j^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & s_j^2 & c_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} & P_{1,24}(\theta_j) &= \begin{pmatrix} c_j^2 & 0 & 0 & s_j^2 \\ 0 & c_j^2 & s_j^2 & 0 \\ s_j^2 & 0 & c_j^2 & 0 \\ 0 & s_j^2 & 0 & c_j^2 \end{pmatrix}
 \end{aligned}$$

Note there are now four mixing angles. The mixing matrices themselves will result from four building-block multiplications, each of which is doubly stochastic by design. Eight exemplars are shown below, chosen for their appealing symmetries.

$$P_{1,4}(\theta_1)P_{1,8}(\theta_2)P_{1,12}(\theta_3)P_{1,16}(\theta_4)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} C_1^2C_2^2C_4^2 + S_1^2S_4^2 & C_1^2S_2^2S_3^2 & C_1^2C_3^2S_2^2 & C_1^2C_2^2S_4^2 + C_4^2S_1^2 \\ C_2^2C_4^2S_1^2 & C_1^2C_3^2 + S_1^2S_2^2S_3^2 & C_1^2S_3^2 + C_3^2S_1^2S_2^2 & C_2^2S_1^2S_4^2 \\ C_1^2C_4^2S_2^2 & C_1^2C_2^2S_3^2 + C_3^2S_1^2 & C_1^2C_2^2C_3^2 + S_1^2S_3^2 & C_1^2S_2^2S_4^2 \\ C_1^2S_4^2 + C_4^2S_1^2S_2^2 & C_2^2S_1^2S_3^2 & C_2^2C_3^2S_1^2 & C_1^2C_4^2 + S_1^2S_2^2S_4^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$P_{1,6}(\theta_1)P_{1,8}(\theta_2)P_{1,10}(\theta_3)P_{1,12}(\theta_4)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} C_2^2C_3^2 + S_2^2S_3^2 & C_2^2C_4^2S_3^2 + C_3^2S_2^2S_4^2 & C_2^2S_3^2S_4^2 + C_3^2C_4^2S_2^2 & 0 \\ 0 & C_1^2C_3^2C_4^2 + S_1^2S_3^2S_4^2 & C_1^2C_3^2S_4^2 + C_4^2S_1^2S_3^2 & C_1^2S_3^2 + C_3^2S_1^2 \\ C_2^2S_3^2 + C_3^2S_2^2 & C_2^2C_3^2S_4^2 + C_4^2S_2^2S_3^2 & C_2^2C_3^2C_4^2 + S_2^2S_3^2S_4^2 & 0 \\ 0 & C_1^2S_3^2S_4^2 + C_3^2C_4^2S_1^2 & C_1^2C_4^2S_3^2 + C_3^2S_1^2S_4^2 & C_1^2C_3^2 + S_1^2S_3^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$P_{1,7}(\theta_1)P_{1,8}(\theta_2)P_{1,12}(\theta_3)P_{1,16}(\theta_4)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} C_1^2C_2^2C_4^2 & C_1^2S_2^2S_3^2 + C_3^2S_1^2 & C_1^2C_3^2S_2^2 + S_1^2S_3^2 & C_1^2C_2^2S_4^2 \\ C_2^2C_4^2S_1^2 & C_1^2C_3^2 + S_1^2S_2^2S_3^2 & C_1^2S_3^2 + C_3^2S_1^2S_2^2 & C_2^2S_1^2S_4^2 \\ C_1^2C_4^2S_2^2 + S_1^2S_4^2 & C_1^2C_2^2S_3^2 & C_1^2C_2^2C_3^2 & C_1^2S_2^2S_4^2 + C_4^2S_1^2 \\ C_1^2S_4^2 + C_4^2S_1^2S_2^2 & C_2^2S_1^2S_3^2 & C_2^2C_3^2S_1^2 & C_1^2C_4^2 + S_1^2S_2^2S_4^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$P_{1,12}(\theta_3)P_{1,16}(\theta_4)P_{1,7}(\theta_1)P_{1,8}(\theta_2)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} C_1^2C_2^2C_4^2 + S_1^2S_2^2S_4^2 & C_4^2S_1^2 & C_1^2C_4^2S_2^2 + C_2^2S_1^2S_4^2 & C_1^2S_4^2 \\ C_1^2S_2^2S_3^2 + C_2^2C_3^2S_1^2 & C_1^2C_3^2 & C_1^2C_2^2S_3^2 + C_3^2S_1^2S_2^2 & S_1^2S_3^2 \\ C_1^2C_3^2S_2^2 + C_2^2S_1^2S_3^2 & C_1^2S_3^2 & C_1^2C_2^2C_3^2 + S_1^2S_2^2S_3^2 & C_3^2S_1^2 \\ C_1^2C_2^2S_4^2 + C_4^2S_1^2S_2^2 & S_1^2S_4^2 & C_1^2S_2^2S_4^2 + C_2^2C_4^2S_1^2 & C_1^2C_4^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$P_{1,22}(\theta_2)P_{1,18}(\theta_3)P_{1,8}(\theta_4)P_{1,16}(\theta_1)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_1^2c_3^2c_4^2 & s_3^2 & c_3^2s_4^2 & c_3^2c_4^2s_1^2 \\ c_1^2c_4^2s_3^2 & c_3^2 & s_3^2s_4^2 & c_4^2s_1^2s_3^2 \\ c_1^2c_2^2s_4^2 + s_1^2s_2^2 & 0 & c_2^2c_4^2 & c_1^2s_2^2 + c_2^2s_1^2s_4^2 \\ c_1^2s_2^2s_4^2 + c_2^2s_1^2 & 0 & c_4^2s_2^2 & c_1^2c_2^2 + s_1^2s_2^2s_4^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$P_{1,16}(\theta_1)P_{1,22}(\theta_2)P_{1,18}(\theta_3)P_{1,8}(\theta_4)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_1^2c_3^2c_4^2 + s_1^2s_2^2s_4^2 & c_1^2s_3^2 & c_1^2c_3^2s_4^2 + c_4^2s_1^2s_2^2 & c_2^2s_1^2 \\ c_4^2s_3^2 & c_3^2 & s_3^2s_4^2 & 0 \\ c_2^2s_4^2 & 0 & c_2^2c_4^2 & s_2^2 \\ c_1^2s_2^2s_4^2 + c_3^2c_4^2s_1^2 & s_1^2s_3^2 & c_1^2c_4^2s_2^2 + c_3^2s_1^2s_4^2 & c_1^2c_2^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$P_{1,8}(\theta_2)P_{1,9}(\theta_1)P_{1,12}(\theta_3)P_{1,22}(\theta_4)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_1^2c_2^2 & s_2^2s_3^2 & c_2^2s_1^2s_4^2 + c_3^2c_4^2s_2^2 & c_2^2c_4^2s_1^2 + c_3^2s_2^2s_4^2 \\ s_1^2 & c_1^2c_3^2 & c_1^2c_4^2s_3^2 & c_1^2s_3^2s_4^2 \\ c_1^2s_2^2 & c_2^2s_3^2 & c_2^2c_3^2c_4^2 + s_1^2s_2^2s_4^2 & c_2^2c_3^2s_4^2 + c_4^2s_1^2s_2^2 \\ 0 & c_3^2s_1^2 & c_1^2s_4^2 + c_4^2s_1^2s_3^2 & c_1^2c_4^2 + s_1^2s_3^2s_4^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$P_{1,10}(\theta_3)P_{1,12}(\theta_4)P_{1,16}(\theta_1)P_{1,9}(\theta_2)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_1^2c_2^2c_3^2 + c_4^2s_2^2s_3^2 & c_2^2c_4^2s_3^2 + c_3^2s_1^2s_2^2 & s_3^2s_4^2 & c_1^2c_3^2s_2^2 + c_2^2c_3^2s_1^2 \\ c_2^2s_1^2s_3^2 + c_3^2c_4^2s_2^2 & c_1^2s_2^2s_3^2 + c_2^2c_3^2c_4^2 & c_3^2s_4^2 & c_1^2c_2^2s_3^2 + s_1^2s_2^2s_3^2 \\ c_1^2c_2^2s_3^2 + c_3^2s_2^2s_4^2 & c_2^2c_3^2s_4^2 + s_1^2s_2^2s_3^2 & c_3^2c_4^2 & c_1^2s_2^2s_3^2 + c_2^2s_1^2s_3^2 \\ c_2^2c_3^2s_1^2 + s_2^2s_3^2s_4^2 & c_1^2c_3^2s_2^2 + c_2^2s_3^2s_4^2 & c_4^2s_3^2 & c_1^2c_2^2c_3^2 + c_3^2s_1^2s_2^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

A more general way to build 4D doubly stochastic matrices is to use the blocks

$$P_{n,k}(\theta_1) = c_1^2 \pi_n + s_1^2 \pi_k \quad \text{for } n,k = 1,\dots,24$$

$$P_{m,q}(\theta_2) = c_2^2 \pi_m + s_2^2 \pi_q \quad \text{for } m,q = 1,\dots,24$$

$$P_{s,v}(\theta_3) = c_3^2 \pi_s + s_3^2 \pi_v \quad \text{for } s,v = 1,\dots,24$$

$$P_{r,y}(\theta_4) = c_4^2 \pi_r + s_4^2 \pi_y \quad \text{for } r,y = 1,\dots,24$$

and form the product

$$P_{n,k}(\theta_1)P_{m,q}(\theta_2)P_{s,v}(\theta_3)P_{r,y}(\theta_4)$$

for selected indices, generating an even greater multitude of mixing matrices. Thus

$$P_{n,k}(\theta_1)P_{m,q}(\theta_2)P_{s,v}(\theta_3)P_{r,y}(\theta_4) =$$

$$\begin{aligned} & (c_1^2 \pi_n + s_1^2 \pi_k)(c_2^2 \pi_m + s_2^2 \pi_q)(c_3^2 \pi_s + s_3^2 \pi_v)(c_4^2 \pi_r + s_4^2 \pi_y) = \\ & c_1^2 c_2^2 c_3^2 c_4^2 p_n p_m p_s p_r + c_1^2 c_2^2 c_3^2 s_4^2 p_n p_m p_s p_y + c_1^2 c_2^2 c_4^2 s_3^2 p_n p_m p_v p_r + \\ & c_1^2 c_2^2 s_3^2 s_4^2 p_n p_m p_v p_y + c_1^2 c_3^2 c_4^2 s_2^2 p_n p_q p_s p_r + c_1^2 c_3^2 s_2^2 s_4^2 p_n p_q p_s p_y + \\ & c_1^2 c_4^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 p_n p_q p_v p_r + c_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 s_4^2 p_n p_q p_v p_y + c_2^2 c_3^2 c_4^2 s_1^2 p_k p_m p_s p_r + \\ & c_2^2 c_3^2 s_1^2 s_4^2 p_k p_m p_s p_y + c_2^2 c_4^2 s_1^2 s_3^2 p_k p_m p_v p_r + c_2^2 s_1^2 s_3^2 s_4^2 p_k p_m p_v p_y + \\ & c_3^2 c_4^2 s_1^2 s_2^2 p_k p_q p_s p_r + c_3^2 s_1^2 s_2^2 s_4^2 p_k p_q p_s p_y + c_4^2 s_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 p_k p_q p_v p_r + \\ & s_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 s_4^2 p_k p_q p_v p_y \end{aligned}$$

The sorted table on p.1 should help simplify the multiple permutation products once numeric indices have been selected, and then generate the corresponding mixing matrix. It is of course true that these permutation coefficients also form a convex set, since they equal the product

$$(c_1^2 + s_1^2)(c_2^2 + s_2^2)(c_3^2 + s_3^2)(c_4^2 + s_4^2) = 1$$

Reference

[1] A. Cusmariu, 'Elementary particle mixings as convex sums of permutations', zenodo.10104280, 2023